

**Investigating the Hypolipidemic Potential of Siddhadhi Ennai: A Molecular Docking and
Computational Analysis Approach**

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Abstract

Purpose: This study aimed to investigate the bioactive substances in siddhadhi ennai, a Siddha Herbo-mineral formulation used for treating hyperlipidemia (HLD) and gynecological disorders. A network pharmacology approach combined with computational tools was employed to elucidate the pharmacological mechanisms of its hypolipidemic activity.

Methods: We integrated network pharmacology, gene enrichment analysis, target prediction, and ligand docking. Initial analysis identified potential target genes related to hypolipidemic activity, including LMDH, LOX5, MDRI, NR1H4, MMPI, CYP19A, SORL, FABP4, FABPL, PPARA, ANDR, and SHBG. Ligand docking was performed on a protein structure (PDB-1HWK) using the Glide module, following site identification via the SiteMap tool. Ligands were prepared with LigPrep, and their ADMET profiles were evaluated using QikProp, followed by molecular dynamics simulations with Desmond over 200 ns.

Results: The network analysis identified 11 target genes associated with hypolipidemic pathways. Docking studies initially showed minimal ligand interactions, leading to the discovery of five alternative binding sites with favorable docking interactions. Subsequent simulations confirmed the stability of ligand-protein interactions, supported by MMGBSA metrics.

Conclusion: This study elucidated the pharmacological and molecular basis of siddhadhi ennai's hypolipidemic effects and showcased the utility of computational tools in drug discovery. The identified target genes and their interaction dynamics indicate significant therapeutic potential against HLD, setting the stage for future drug screening and enhancing our understanding of protein-ligand interactions in hypolipidemic therapy.

Keywords: Siddhadhi ennai, hypolipidemia, HMG-CoA, cardiovascular health, lipid metabolism

Introduction:

Hyperlipidemia (HLD) is a globally prevalent metabolic disorder linked to cardiovascular diseases such as atherosclerosis, diabetes, coronary heart disease, and hypertension (Genest et al., 2009; Navar-Boggan et al., 2015; Nelson, 2012).^{1,2,3} It is characterized by elevated triglycerides and LDL-C, reduced HDL-C, and increased total cholesterol (Zeng et al., 2020).⁴ With rising morbidity, HLD is a major public health issue. While statins are common lipid-lowering agents, they can cause dose-dependent muscle-related side effects (Hippisley-Cox and Coupland 2010; Hoffman et al., 2012; du Souich, Roederer, and Dufour 2017; Wang et al., 2021).^{5,6,7,8} Thus, alternative lipid metabolism therapies are needed.

In Siddha medicine, obesity is classified based on various etiologies and symptoms (Sureka 2019).⁹ Siddhadhi ennai, a herbo-mineral Siddha formula with 12 ingredients, is used for disorders including HLD and gynecological issues (Vinodini et al., 2018).¹⁰ This study investigates its hypolipidemic and anti-obesity mechanisms. Unlike Western medicine, Siddha emphasizes synergistic effects of compounds (Chu et al., 2015; El-Tantawy and Temraz, 2019).^{11,12} Network pharmacology, focusing on drug-disease-target interactions, was applied to clarify the multi-ingredient, multitarget actions of Siddhadhi ennai in HLD. Molecular docking assessed the orientation and stability of protein-ligand interactions to support drug design (Abdolmaleki et al., 2021; Muhammed & Aki-Yalcin, 2022; Rajkhowa & Deka, 2016).^{13,14,15}

Materials and Methods:**1. GC-MS analysis:**

Siddhadhi ennai GC-MS analysis was performed on a GC Clarius 500 PerkinElmer instrument. A 30 0.25 mm 1 pmf Elite-1 (100% dimethylpolysiloxane) column was used for data collection.

Helium was used as the carrier gas with a 1 millilitre/min flow rate in split mode (10:1). After setting the injector temperature to 250°C, a 2 µL sample aliquot was injected into the column. After the samples were held at 110°C for two minutes, the temperature in the GC oven increased to 200°C without being held constant. At a 5°C/min program rate, the samples were held for nine minutes at 280°C. The injector and detector were set at 250°C and 280°C, respectively. The temperature of the ion source was kept constant at 200°C. The detector was run in scan mode from 45-450 amu (atomic mass units) to obtain the mass spectra of the compounds in the samples by electron ionisation at 70 eV. Forty-five to 450 DA fragments were maintained at a scan interval of 0.5 seconds. The total running time was 36 minutes (Sermakkani, M. and Thangapandian, V., 2012).¹⁶

2. Selection of bioactive compounds:

Based on the GC-MS analysis, the various components, along with their retention times and percentages, were identified in 57 compounds in the crude extract of the siddhadhiennai. The mass spectra of the identified compounds from siddhadhiennai are presented in Fig. 1 and Table [Table 1 (supplementary data)]. The bioactive compounds used were 3-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyanisole, 13-hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one, lignoceric acid, octanoic acid, oleic acid and Z,Z-8,10-Hexadecadien-1-ol. The pharmacological activity of these compounds is tabulated in Table 1, which was further analysed through network pharmacology analysis.

2. Compound library and database preparation:

The chemical constituents present in the siddhadhiennai were subjected to GC-MS analysis, and mass spectral analysis was carried out to elucidate the structure and masses of the various phytoconstituents present in the species. Initially, a primary database of the compounds was

created by identifying the PubChem CID numbers of the compounds using their IUPAC names. Then, using the PubChem CID number, both two-dimensional structure and SMILES (chemical identifier) data were obtained, and a secondary database of the compounds was constructed, along with complete details such as molecular weight, molecular formula, SMILES, and 2D structure. (Ghannay, Kadri, and Aouadi 2020).¹⁷

3. Primary screening of physiochemical properties, bioactivity, and toxicology:

With the current database as an initial source, primary virtual screening of compounds was carried out to determine their physiochemical properties and pharmacological nature. The Swiss ADME web server was utilised to predict the solubility, lipophilicity, adsorption nature, excretion rate, and interactions with different metabolic receptors; these parameters were also analysed and tabulated (Da Rocha et al., 2022).¹⁸ The bioactivity of the compounds was predicted using the PASS (prediction of activity spectra) online web server, and toxicity was predicted using the GUSAR (General Unrestricted Structure-Activity Relationships) online server (Mayr et al., 2020).¹⁹ The results were subsequently tabulated. (Table 2).

Out of the 12 bioactive components identified from the GC-MS analysis, only 6 showed significant interactions with hypolipidemic genes.

4. Target prediction and pathway analysis:

The interactions of different protein targets and their respective genes with phytochemical compounds were predicted by investigating protein target prediction databases such as the Therapeutic Target Database (TTD), Swiss Target Prediction, and Binding database online servers. (Kong et al., 2020).²⁰ The respective genes of the predicted protein targets were subsequently identified using the UniProt database and GenBank. Finally, a string database was

utilised to carry out a gene ontology enrichment study to determine the molecular functions, biological processes, and cellular localisation of the predicted protein targets. Pathway analysis was carried out to predict the role of protein targets in metabolic pathways, Reactome pathways, and disease–gene interaction pathways. (Liu et al., 2022).²¹

5. Network design and visualisation:

Initially, all the data were formatted as CSV files containing compound-protein target prediction, protein–gene interaction, and gene-disease-metabolic pathway predictions. The predictions were subsequently drawn as networks using Cytoscape 3.9.1 software, and the degree of the network was determined with the observed gene count for each active pathway analysis (Wang et al., 2021).⁸

6. Targeted disease-based approach:

A similar approach was used for specific disease-based studies. Initially, the NCBI Gene and DrugBank databases were utilised to identify the target protein responsible for a particular disease. The UniProt database was subsequently used to identify the genes of the predicted protein targets. Finally, a string database was utilised to perform Gene Ontology enrichment studies. Common protein targets between the compound and disease pathway analyses were used to construct a joint network comprising the compound and disease-based investigative approaches (Chen et al., 2016).²²

7. Docking study methodology

7.1 Protein Preparation and Selection

The protein structure utilised in this study was retrieved from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) (Berman, 2000) under the accession code PDB-1HWK. The selection criteria for this protein

included the presence of a co-crystallised ligand, high-quality X-ray diffraction data, the absence of missing loops or chains, and no reported mutations. The structure was prepared using the Maestro interface of Schrödinger (Sastry et al., 2013),²³ where hydrogen atoms were added, and the ionisation states at physiological pH were assigned.

7.2 Site Identification Using SiteMap

The use of the SiteMap (Halgren, 2009) tool in Schrödinger enabled the identification of six potential alternative binding sites within the protein structure. Initial docking attempts with the co-crystallised ligand revealed minimal interactions and low docking scores, prompting a more detailed analysis of the protein's binding characteristics. Distinct SiteScores, guiding subsequent grid generation and docking studies, characterised each predicted site. Given the limited number of ligands available for analysis, all five predicted binding sites were selected for docking to explore their potential interactions further

8. Docking Preparations

8.1 Grid Generation:

Co-crystal ligands were utilised for grid generation. All six suggestions generated by the sitemap were considered in preparing the grid. Grids were generated independently for each proposed binding site using the Glide Grid module of Schrödinger.

8.2 Ligand Preparation for Docking:

The six selected ligands were prepared for docking using the LigPrep module of Schrödinger, applying default parameters (Johnston et al., 2023).²⁴ The ligands were generated in their most stable protonation states and minimised to ensure optimal geometry for docking experiments.

9. Docking Protocol:

Docking the prepared ligands into the generated grids was carried out using the XP docking protocol in the Glide module of Schrödinger (Friesner et al., 2006).²⁵ Default settings were maintained throughout the docking process unless stated otherwise. The top-ranked conformations for each ligand, based on docking scores and binding interactions, were noted for further analysis. The docking score cutoff for MD simulations was kept at ≤ -4 Kcal/mol.

10. ADMET Analysis:

The ADMET profiles of the docking ligands were assessed using the QikProp (Schrödinger Release 2024-1: QikProp, Schrödinger, LLC, New York, 2024) module of Schrödinger. This analysis aimed to evaluate the ligands' drug-like properties and pharmacokinetic profiles, informing the selection of candidates with favourable characteristics for further investigation.

11. Molecular Dynamics Simulations:

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations were performed using the Desmond tool (Bowers et al., 2006),²⁶ considering poses that yielded higher docking scores. The system was constructed using the SPC water model and neutralised based on the overall charge of the system, employing counter ions. Subsequently, the system underwent minimisation for 100 picoseconds using the Desmond minimisation module. The most stable frames were selected for the production MD simulation, which ran for 200 ns (nanoseconds) with NVT parameters. The entire simulation was recorded in 1000 frames, which carries information of about 200 picoseconds. The root mean square deviation (RMSD) and root mean square fluctuation (RMSF) of the protein. At the same time, the complex with individual ligands was plotted, along with structural conformations,

interaction landscape throughout the simulation that includes bond rotations, intra-molecular hydrogen bonds, and hydrophobic interactions.

12. Post-MD Analysis:

The Simulation Interaction Diagram within Schrödinger was utilised to analyse the trajectory data obtained from the MD simulations. Key metrics, including RMSD, RMSF, secondary structural elements, ligand RMSF, and torsional angles, were calculated and visualised. Additionally, MMGBSA calculations were conducted on every 10th frame to derive binding free energy estimates and to analyse the stability of ligand-protein interactions throughout the simulation (Amadei et al., 1993).²⁷

Results

For GC–MS analysis:

The PubChem database (<http://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>) was used to download the 2D structures (in sdf format) and SMILES codes for 12 active components; 6 bioactive compounds exhibited hypolipidemic activity. These 6 bioactive compounds were predicted using the Swiss ADME web tool (<http://www.swissadme.ch/index.php>). The absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) parameters were also used to predict the blood-brain barrier (BBB). A complete open-source tool called Toxtree (version 3.1.0.1851) was used to perform the toxicity study. It is capable of estimating toxic dangers by predicting various toxicological endpoints using various modules, including carcinogenicity prediction. The predicted absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, BBB, toxicity, and carcinogenicity profiles of the eleven bioactive compounds are tabulated in Table [Table 2 – (supplementary files)].

Figure 1: GC-MS chromatogram of siddhadhi ennai.

Table 1: Bioactive compounds of siddhadhi ennai and their pharmacological activity

		(Malayaman et al., 2019) ³⁰
5	Lignoceric acid, TMS derivative	Antibacterial (Awaad et al., 2017) ³¹
6	Hexadecanoic acid, 1-(hydroxymethyl)-1,2-ethanediyl ester	Antioxidant, hypocholesterolemic, antiandrogenic, hemolytic, Alpha reductase inhibitor (Rout et al. 2023) ³²
7	Oleic acid, 3-hydroxypropyl ester	Anitmicrobial and antioxidant (Fadzir et al., 2018) ³³
8	Diethylene glycol dibenzoate	Hypolipidemic activity (Santangeli et al., 2018) ³⁴
9	Dodecanoic acid, 1-(hydroxymethyl)-1,2-ethanediyl ester	used as emulsifiers for cream, milky lotion, and hair conditioner (Yakubu, Otitoju, and Onwuka 2017) ³⁵
10	13-Hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one	chemotherapeutic activity (Dirar et al., 2014) ³⁶
11	10-Undecenoyl chloride	No activity
12	1-Hydroxy-3-(octanoyloxy)propan-2-yl decanoate	Antimicrobial and Antioxidant Activities (Nivetha et al., 2021) ³⁷
13	Z,Z-8,10-Hexadecadien-1-ol	Hypolipidemic activity (Rachmawati et al., 2022) ³⁸

Table 2: Primary screening of the physiochemical properties, bioactivity, and toxicity of siddhadhiennai

S. No	Molecule Name	Molecule Weight (g/mol)	Drug Likeness	Bioavailability Score	Structure	Pub Chem ID
1	3-tert-Butyl-4-hydroxyanisole	180.24	1.10	0.55		8456

2	13-Hexyloxacyclotride c-10-en-2-one.1	280.45	0.95	0.55		566650
3	Lignoceric acid	440.82	1.30	0.55		522540
4	Octanoic acid	144.21	0.54	0.85		379
5	Oleic acid, 3-hydroxypropyl ester.1	340.54	0.52	0.55		5352775
6	Z,Z-8,10-Hexadecadien-1-ol	238.41	1.11	0.55		5364617

Disease pathway prediction analysis

Hypolipidemic activity was taken as the choice parameter for considering disease pathway analysis. With hypolipidemic activity as the main keyword, an internet search was carried out in the general databases containing the disease and its related gene details; the following genes and their respective protein targets were found to be involved in the hypolipidemic activity, and the same was used for further studies (Su H et al., 2023).

Figure 2: Biological process of the selected genes and their respective protein targets.

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Figure 3: Molecular functions of the selected genes and their respective protein targets.

With the aforementioned genes and proteins as the preliminary targets for HLD, initial gene ontology enrichment studies were carried out using the STRING database, and the results were utilised to construct a pictorial bar chart comprising the major molecular, biological, and metabolic functions of the genes (Fig. 2). Among the 13 gene targets identified in the present study, eight were found to be directly involved in lipid metabolism in addition to common

biological functions. Other important functions, including fatty acid transport, cellular lipid metabolism, positive regulation of adipose tissue, negative regulation of cholesterol storage, and lipid localisation, were related to hypolipidemic activity and were found to be the predominant functions of the selected gene targets. Therefore, these selected genes and their respective protein targets can be taken as a primary source for screening the hypolipidemic activity of the compounds (Wang et al., 2021).

Similarly, major molecular functions of the selected protein targets were analysed using the STRING database. The results are depicted as a bar chart with the false discovery rate (FDR) and gene count as major axes. Monocarboxylic acid binding, fatty acid binding, lipid binding, and long-chain fatty acid transporter activity were found to be the common metabolic functions of the selected genes and were also related to hypolipidemic activity (Fig. 3).

Pathway analysis was carried out to understand the actual involvement of the selected gene targets in the study's associated disease. Kegg pathway, Reactome pathway, and Wiki pathway analyses were carried out, and the results are depicted in Fig. 4. The involvement of the selected genes in pathways such as triglyceride catabolism, fatty acid transporter, steroidogenesis, and receptors in lipids proves that the targets were selected correctly.

Protein-protein interaction study

The selected target proteins were then subjected to protein-protein interaction analysis using an online STRING database web server. Of the 13 protein targets, 11 were found to be interconnected, while a few proteins seemed to have more than two interactions. Thus, compounds that have a binding affinity for any of the selected 13 protein targets can be effective toward the entire metabolic pathway and initiate a cascade of reactions (Fig. 5 and 6).

Figure 4: Pathway analysis of the selected genes and their respective protein targets.

Figure 5: String database network image of protein-protein interactions.

Figure 6: Cytoscape-processed network image of protein-protein interactions.

Disease-compound interactions and network

In this study, we identified/mapped 13 genes with hypolipemic activity (Table 3), and there were 12 active compounds, out of which 6 were known to be hypolipidemic. We docked these compounds against HMG-CoA and identified three bioactive compounds that interact significantly

with HMG-CoA. This gene was the major target of more than 6 compounds, followed by CYP19A1, FABP4, FABP1, PPAR γ , and PPAR α , which are common targets between the disease and compound prediction datasets (Fig. 7).

Figure 7: Combined network compound-gene-disease analysis.

Table 3: Common gene targets between the disease and compound prediction datasets

Gene Detail	Protein ID (UniProt)	No. of compounds having the same gene target	Compounds list
HMDH_HUMAN	P04035	6	3-tert-Butyl-4-hydroxyanisole,13-Hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one.1, Lignoceric acid,Octanoic acid, <i>Oleic acid</i> , 3- <i>hydroxypropyl ester.1</i> , Z,Z-8,10-Hexadecadien- 1-ol
LOX5_HUMAN	P09917	2	Lignoceric acid, Octanoic acid,
MDR1_HUMAN	P08183	2	Lignoceric acid, Octanoic acid,
NR1H4_HUMAN	Q96RI1	3	Lignoceric acid, Octanoic acid, Z,Z-8,10-Hexadecadien-1-ol
MMP1_HUMAN	P03956	0	-
CYP19A_HUMAN	P11511	5	Hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one, Lignoceric acid, Octanoic acid, <i>Oleic acid</i> , 3- <i>hydroxypropyl ester.1</i> , Z,Z-8,10- Hexadecadien-1-ol
SORL_HUMAN	Q92673	0	-
FABP4_HUMAN	P15090	5	Hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one, Lignoceric acid, Octanoic acid, <i>Oleic acid</i> , 3- <i>hydroxypropyl ester.1</i> , Z,Z-8,10-

			Hexadecadien-1-ol
FABPL_HUMAN	P07148	3	Lignoceric acid, Octanoic acid, Z,Z-8,10-Hexadecadien-1-ol
PPAR γ _HUMAN	P37231	5	Lignoceric acid, Octanoic acid,
PPAR α _HUMAN	Q07869	5	3-tert-Butyl-4-hydroxyanisole, Lignoceric acid, Octanoic acid, <i>Oleic acid</i> , 3-hydroxypropyl ester.1, Z,Z-8,10-Hexadecadien-1-ol
ANDR_HUMAN	P10275	2	Lignoceric acid, Octanoic acid,
SHBG_HUMAN	P04278	2	Lignoceric acid, Octanoic acid,

Site map results:

The site map identified five sites within the receptor, and their respective site scores were tabulated in Table 4. These sites were subsequently utilised to construct grids, which were subsequently employed for ligand docking through the XP protocol.

ADMET results:

The selection of ligands is a crucial step in discovering new drugs or repurposing projects. ADMET results have become an indispensable tool in selecting ligands for drug screening. They allow us to eliminate ligands that lack favourable ADME properties from our screening libraries, thereby reducing the number of ligands to be screened and the time required for computation. Results from the QikProp tool of Schrödinger were tabulated in Table 4.

Docking results:

Results from the XP docking protocol were recorded in Table 4.

In our docking results site 1 from the sitemap tool has produced better results compare to the other binding sites predicted by the Site map (Table 4) and the Lignoceric acid has a docking score of -5.695 Kcal/mol (Fig 8, Fig 9) and followed by 13-Hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one with the docking score of -5.317 Kcal/mol(Fig. 10, Fig. 11), Oleic acid, 3-hydroxypropyl ester.1 with the docking score of -4.497Kcal/mol (Fig.12, 13).

Figure 8: Ligand interaction Diagram of Lignoceric acid with HMG-CoA-predicted binding site -1.

Figure 9: Binding pose of Lignoceric acid with HMG-COA-predicted binding site -1.

Figure 10: Ligand interaction Diagram of Hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one.1 with HMG-COA-predicted binding site -1.

Figure 11: Binding pose of Hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one.1 with HMG-COA-predicted binding site -1.

Figure 12: Ligand interaction Diagram of Oleic acid, 3-hydroxypropyl ester.1 with HMG-COA-predicted binding site -1.

Figure 13: Binding pose of Oleic acid, 3-hydroxypropyl ester.1 with HMG-COA-predicted binding site -1

Figure 14: RMSD plot of Lignoceric acid in maroon color, and the protein RMSD is plotted in blue color, the time frame is 200 ns.

Entry Name	SiteScore	volume	Ligand	Docking score (Kcal/mol)

Figure 15: RMSD plot of 13-Hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one in maroon color, and the protein RMSD is plotted in blue color; the time frame is 200 ns.

Table 4: Site-Specific Binding Site Predictions and Docking Scores for Selected Ligands

Site- 1				
sitemap_1HWK_site_1	0.919	708.638	Lignoceric acid.1	-5.695
			13-Hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one	-5.317
			Oleic acid, 3-hydroxypropyl ester.1	-4.497
			3-tert-Butyl-4-hydroxyanisole.1	-3.854
			Z,Z-8,10-Hexadecadien-1-ol.1	-2.288
			Octanoic acid.1	-1.71
Site-2				
sitemap_1HWK_site_2	0.893	268.226	Lignoceric acid.1	-3.038
			13-Hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one	-2.994
			Oleic acid, 3-hydroxypropyl ester.1	-2.818
			3-tert-Butyl-4-hydroxyanisole.1	-0.911
			Z,Z-8,10-Hexadecadien-1-ol.1	-0.378
			Octanoic acid.1	0.514
Site-3				

sitemap_1HWK_site_3	0.874	206.829	Lignoceric acid.1	-2.97
			13-Hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one	-2.721
			Oleic acid, 3-hydroxypropyl ester.1	-1.676
			3-tert-Butyl-4-hydroxyanisole.1	-1.457
			Z,Z-8,10-Hexadecadien-1-ol.1	-0.775
			Octanoic acid.1	0.614
Site-4				
sitemap_1HWK_site_4	0.896	104.615	Lignoceric acid.1	-3.525
			13-Hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one	-3.086
			Oleic acid, 3-hydroxypropyl ester.1	-2.795
			3-tert-Butyl-4-hydroxyanisole.1	-2.666
			Z,Z-8,10-Hexadecadien-1-ol.1	-0.973
			Octanoic acid.1	-0.468
Site-5				
sitemap_1HWK_site_5	0.893	83.349	Lignoceric acid.1	-2.659

			13-Hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one	-2.374
			Oleic acid, 3-hydroxypropyl ester.1	-2.269
			3-tert-Butyl-4-hydroxyanisole.1	-2.154
			Z,Z-8,10-Hexadecadien-1-ol.1	-1.315
			Octanoic acid.1	1.001

Along with 3-tert-Butyl-4-hydroxyanisole with a Docking score of -3.854 Kcal/mol, Z, Z-8,10-Hexadecadien-1-ol with the docking score of -2.288 Kcal/mol, and Octanoic acid with the docking score of -1.71 Kcal/mol. Ligands with a docking score of more than or equal to -4 Kcal/mol were considered for the Molecular Dynamics Simulations.

Molecular Dynamics

RMSD data of both ligands and receptors were plotted using a simulation interaction diagram.

In molecular dynamics studies, RMSD fluctuations around 1-3 angstrom (Å) are generally considered stable. We have observed that out of all three molecules (that have cleared the Docking score cutoff of -4.0 Kcal/mol) taken up for molecular dynamics, 13-Hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one (Fig. 15), and Oleic acid, the 3-hydroxypropyl ester is stable in the binding pocket throughout the simulations (Fig. 16), whereas the Lignoceric acid (Fig. 14) was found to be unstable. These ligands were compared with the co-crystal ligand Atorvastatin (Fig. 17). The protein backbone is also stable with fluctuations around 3 Å with a deviation of

1Å. Other ligands have shown unfavourable binding with the protein since the RMSD and RMSF values fluctuate with a difference of 5 ± 1 Å. Most of the interactions demonstrated by the Oleic acid, 3-hydroxypropyl ester were hydrophobic interactions and water bridges (Fig. 18).

Figure 16: RMSD plot of Oleic acid, 3-hydroxypropyl ester in maroon color, and the protein RMSD is plotted in blue color, time frame is 200 ns.

Figure 17: RMSD plot of crystalized atorvastatin ester in maroon color, and the protein RMSD is plotted in blue color; the time frame is 200 ns.

Figure 18: Ligand interactions histogram, Oleic acid, 3-hydroxypropyl ester in maroon color, and the protein RMSD is plotted in blue, the time frame is 200 ns.

Figure 19: Post-MD MMGBSA of the ligand and protein complexes.

Post-MD MMGBSA of the ligand and protein complexes were recorded (Fig. 19). The dG-Bind values measure the binding energy of the complex in comparison to the free, unbound protein. In our observation, ligand 2 (13-Hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one) and ligand 3 (Oleic acid, 3-hydroxypropyl ester) had better energy profiles compared to the co-crystal ligand in the structure.

Discussion:

HLD is characterized by elevated TC, TG, and LDL-C, and decreased HDL-C, reflecting a disturbance in lipid metabolism. Oxidative stress, inflammation, cholesterol, and other factors may contribute to dyslipidemia-induced HLD. Siddhadhiennai, recognized for its pharmacological effects on gynecological illnesses such as amenorrhea, dysmenorrhea,

leucorrhea, menorrhagia, and HLD, was investigated using network pharmacology to elucidate its mechanism, focusing on its multiple ingredients, targets, and pathways against HLD.

Network pharmacology analysis identified six key active compounds—3-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyanisole, 13-hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one, lignoceric acid, oleic acid, 3-hydroxypropyl ester, and Z,Z-8,10-hexadecadien-1-ol—as potentially effective in treating HLD. Eleven targets were associated with siddhadhiennai's efficacy, including HMGCR, LOX5, CYP19A, MDR-1, NR1H4, FABP4, FABPL, PPAR γ , PPAR α , ANDR, and SHBG.

HMGCR Gene (3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-CoA reductase):

In vitro studies demonstrate the active compound's effect on the HMGCR gene, encoding HMG-CoA reductase—the rate-limiting enzyme in cholesterol synthesis. This enzyme is inhibited by cholesterol, causing internalisation and degradation of LDL by the LDL receptor. The compound likely inhibits HMG-CoA reductase gene expression, reducing enzyme activity, increasing hepatic LDL receptor expression, and thus reducing plasma LDL and total cholesterol. This mechanism mirrors statins, widely used as HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors in HLD (NCBI GeneID: 3156; Ose et al., 2010).⁴⁰ Statins inhibit cholesterol production by blocking mevalonate synthesis.

ALOX5:

ALOX5 is essential for leukotriene (LT) synthesis from arachidonic acid. LTs induce proinflammatory signaling via BLT and CysLT receptors. LTB₄ promotes leukocyte chemotaxis, vascular inflammation, and atherosclerosis. In resting neutrophils, ALOX5 is cytoplasmic; upon activation, LTB₄ relocates to the nuclear membrane to begin biosynthesis. The compound is a substrate for and likely inhibits ALOX5, producing hypolipidemic effects, though subsequent atherosclerotic effects are unassessed (NCBI GeneID: 240). Both human and mouse adipocytes

secrete LT, possibly causing insulin resistance and immune cell recruitment to adipose tissue. In mice, genetic or pharmacologic 5-LOX pathway blockade reduces insulin resistance and adipose macrophages (Mothe-Satney et al., 2012).⁴¹ Mice lacking BLT1, the LTB₄ receptor, show less adipose macrophage infiltration and greater insulin sensitivity (Spite et al., 2011).⁴²

MDR-1:

The MDR-1 gene encodes an ATP-binding cassette transporter that functions as an ATP-dependent drug efflux pump, crucial for hepatic drug uptake, especially statins, to act on hepatic HMGCR. The compound's action through HMGCR suggests that MDR-1 mutations could diminish hepatic uptake and siddhadhiennai efficacy (NCBI GeneID: 5243). A cohort study found 3435T carriers had higher ApoA1, HDL's main apolipoprotein, than CC and CT carriers. ABCB1 and ABCB039 are implicated in cholesterol homeostasis (Jeannesson et al., 2009).⁴³ ABCB1 modulates cholesterol trafficking, including production, esterification, and export to HDL (Garrigues, Escargueil, and Phane Orłowski 2002).⁴⁴ ABCB1 polymorphisms influence ApoA1 plasma levels by altering cholesterol efflux to HDL (Jeannesson et al., 2009).⁴³ P-glycoprotein (P-gp) may influence statin-induced HDL changes (Kajinami et al., 2004).⁴⁵ Atorvastatin is a P-gp substrate, and MDR1 gene expression variations affect atorvastatin response (Kajinami et al., 2004).⁴⁵ Hoffmeyer et al. predicted that MDR1 C3435T TT genotype doubles drug efflux, raising tissue concentration and oral bioavailability and is linked to over twofold lower duodenal P-gp protein expression than CC genotype (Hoffmeyer et al., 2000).⁴⁶

NR1H4 (nuclear hormone receptor):

NR1H4 encodes a ligand-activated transcription factor that serves as a bile acid receptor. Upon binding bile acids, NR1H4 interacts with DNA to regulate bile acid-related gene expression. As a substrate for NR1H4, the compound likely impacts bile acid production and distribution,

contributing to hypolipidemic effects (NCBI GeneID: 9971). Nuclear receptors (NRs) control genes involved in metabolism, xenobiotics, development, and phase transcription, and bind a range of synthetic and natural ligands. The bile acid receptor FXR controls hepatic inflammation, gluconeogenesis, and lipogenesis for metabolic homeostasis. FXR reduces NAFLD pathophysiology and is key in inflammation, glucose/lipid metabolism, and cholesterol/bile acid metabolism (Kim et al., 2016).⁴⁷ FXR agonists manage and prevent NAFLD. However, FXR's role in cholesterol metabolism remains debated; FXR-null mice have higher plasma HDL, lower HDL, and increased LDL when FXR transcription is inhibited (Urizar et al., 2002).⁴⁸ FXR-null mice are protected from hepatic steatosis, diet-induced obesity, and glucose intolerance (Prawitt et al., 2011).⁴⁹ Thus, FXR agonism's effects on cholesterol metabolism need clarification.

FABP4 and FABP1 (fatty acid binding proteins):

FABP genes encode cytoplasmic proteins binding long-chain fatty acids, vital for uptake, transport, and metabolism. The compound, a substrate for these, may modulate fatty acid synthesis and transport, supporting its hypolipidemic effect (NCBI GeneID: 2167; NCBI GeneID: 2168). FABP4 interacts with hormone-sensitive lipase (HSL) to promote lipolysis; only holo FABP4 increases lipolytic activity, likely by scavenging FAs from HSL. A functional link exists between FABP4, Cgi-58 (an ATGL activator), and ATGL (fatty triacylglycerol lipase); FABP4 and Cgi-58 contact enhances ATGL activity. FABP1 downregulation decreases FA uptake and transport via GLP-1 receptor activation, reducing oleate-induced steatosis in HepG2 cells, indicating a role in NAFLD. The human FABP1 coding region contains an SNP (T94A) linked to metabolic disorders and blood lipid anomalies (Storch and Corsico 2023).⁵⁰

PPAR- γ and PPAR- α :

PPAR genes encode nuclear receptor subtypes (α , δ , γ), forming heterodimers with RXRs to regulate genes for cholesterol metabolism, proliferation, and inflammation. PPAR- α targets genes for lipid metabolism, while PPAR- γ regulates glucose balance and adipogenesis. The compound's action on these genes underpins its hypolipidemic effect (NCBI GeneID: 5468; NCBI GeneID: 5465). PPAR- α activators inhibit obesity in animals by enhancing hepatic FA oxidation and lowering circulating TG, reducing adipose growth and hyperplasia, and appear estrogen-regulated, acting with sexual dimorphism on lipid metabolism. Estrogen suppresses PPAR- α 's effects on obesity/lipid metabolism. PPAR- γ is essential for adipocyte differentiation; null adipocytes have diminished differentiation marker expression and fat accumulation (Tyagi et al., 2011).⁵¹

CYP19A1:

CYP19A1 encodes a CYP450 family enzyme for drug metabolism, lipid/cholesterol/steroid production, and aromatase activity. Mutations alter aromatase activity and estrogen synthesis. The active compound is a CYP19A1 substrate, possibly affecting estrogen synthesis and reproductive function. CYP19A1 mutations may alter pharmacological response, warranting further study on menstrual cycle impacts and pharmacological variability (NCBI GeneID: 1588). CYP19A1 and SERPINE1 are major antihyperlipidemic targets and prognostic biomarkers for metabolism (Hu et al., 2019; Sha et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2021).^{52,53,54}

Sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG):

SHBG regulates bioactive free sex hormones, correlating positively with HDL-C and genetically influenced. Low SHBG is linked to obesity, dyslipidemia, and hyperinsulinemia; its role in low HDL-C warrants study (Hergenç et al., 1999; Yasui et al., 2008).^{55,56} In differentiated 3T3-L1 adipocytes, SHBG alters RNA levels for lipid metabolism. After 18 hours of 20 nM SHBG

treatment, levels of factors for triglyceride production/adipogenic differentiation (CEBP- α , PPAR- γ , SREBP1) drop, as do genes for ACRP30, FAS, ACSL1, PEPCK, PGC1 β , HSL, MGL, GLUT4, and FABP4, while AGT and ATGL rise. No significant change was observed for PGC1 α , CEBP β , PPAR- α , UCP1, ChREBP, or CPT1A. This indicates SHBG causes differentiation by downregulating essential lipid metabolism genes (Yamazaki et al., 2018).⁵⁷

Docking Analysis

Molecular docking studies further supported the interaction of active compounds with key target proteins involved in lipid metabolism. The docking analysis identified favourable binding interactions with HMG-CoA reductase HMGCR (Friesner et al., 2004),⁵⁸ an enzyme that plays a crucial role in cholesterol biosynthesis. Notably, oleic acid, 3-hydroxypropyl ester, and 13-Hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one exhibited strong docking scores, suggesting their potential to inhibit HMGCR function like statins.

The observed interactions suggest that active compounds in Siddhadhi Ennai may enhance lipid utilisation and reduce plasma triglyceride levels. Furthermore, interactions with FABP4 and FABPL indicate a role in fatty acid transport and metabolism, further supporting the hypolipidemic effects.

Molecular Dynamics Simulation

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations provided insights into the stability of ligand-protein interactions. RMSD and RMSF analysis confirmed the stable binding of oleic acid, 3-hydroxypropyl ester, and 13-Hexyloxacyclotridec-10-en-2-one with HMGCR over a 200-ns simulation (Bowers et al., 2006).⁵⁹ The MMGBSA binding energy calculations further validated the strong affinity of these compounds toward their respective protein targets, reinforcing their therapeutic potential.

Comparison with Existing Hypolipidemic Agents

Current lipid-lowering therapies, including statins, fibrates, and bile acid sequestrants, exhibit limitations such as muscle-related adverse effects and hepatotoxicity (Wilkins & Lloyd-Jones., 2021).⁶⁰ Siddhadhi ennai, a traditional herbo-mineral formulation, offers a natural alternative with potential multi-target efficacy and reduced side effects. Its ability to interact with multiple targets involved in lipid metabolism suggests a holistic approach to HLD treatment.

Conclusion and Future Directions

The findings from this study highlight the pharmacological potential of siddhadhi ennai in managing hyperlipidemia through a network-based mechanism targeting key regulatory pathways in lipid metabolism. Further in vitro and in vivo studies are warranted to validate these computational predictions and explore the clinical efficacy of siddhadhi ennai in lipid-lowering therapy.

Conclusion

- Of the 13 genes selected for the study, 11 were found to be directly associated with the hypolipidemic activity observed in the present study.
- The predicted molecular, metabolic, and biological functions of the selected genes were related to hypolipidemic activity
- Metabolic pathway analysis revealed direct relationships between the selected genes and various vital pathways associated with hypolipidemic activity
- Common target genes between the compound prediction and disease prediction datasets were found and utilised to analyse the effect of the compound on hypolipidemic activity

- In conclusion, significant genes associated with hypolipidemic activity were also found to be vital targets of these compounds; hence, the polyherbal extract can have vibrant activity against HLD.

Author Contributions

- Sabari Anandh J V: Supervised the study, curated data, prepared the compound library, correlated pharmacological activities, and contributed to manuscript drafting.
- Nileshraj Govindaraj: Contributed to the validation of the traditional Siddha formulation and critically reviewed the manuscript.
- Gayam Prasanna Kumar Reddy: Performed molecular docking, molecular dynamics simulations, and ADMET analysis.
- Lavanya Kesavan: Conducted GC-MS analysis and identified bioactive compounds.
- Pugazhandhi Bakthavatchalam: Carried out target prediction, pathway analysis, and network pharmacology modelling.
- Syed Mushraf: Led project administration and conceptualisation, designed the methodology, critically revised the manuscript, and served as the corresponding author.

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Declarations

Data availability: The datasets used and analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author (Mushraf Syed) on reasonable request via email: smushraf@auamed.net, sydmusharraf@gmail.com

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